

**Shashi Tharoor, Ambedkar:
A Life, Alpha Book Company,
New Delhi, 2022
pp. xii + 226, Rs. 599/=**

Political Discourse
9(1), June 2023
pp. 113-115

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Ambedkar has become an icon not only for the Dalits but for the whole world. Tharoor has been a renowned scholar around the world. This book was written in the form of a biography of Dr. Ambedkar. The author started with the painful experiences of Ambedkar during his childhood. When Ambedkar was a boy, they paid double the price of a cart due to being a Mahar of Maharashtra. In Indian society, the Mahar caste was or is invisible. Hindus did not accept food and water from their hands, even though they were aware that untouchables' sweat could pollute them. Mahars were engaged in various menial jobs, such as watchmen. Similarly, Ambedkar's family played a significant role in the community, as did those working in textiles, the army, etc. Later on, Ambedkar enriched the prestidigitation of the family by getting the highest marks at his school in 1907.

Like that other untold story and the custom of the times, Ambedkar was married to a nine-year-old Mahar girl, Rami, later renamed Ramabai. She was standing with him at all times. Ambedkar was the man of his experiment, who was not mad for reading but quite devoted, and seeing his devotion to the love of reading, the Maharaja of Baroda, Sir Sayaji Rao Gaekwad, granted him a scholarship of Rs. 25 per month. After graduating, he was awarded another scholarship from the maharaja to study in the United States of America for three years at a monthly rate of £ 11.50. In the 1913s, Ambedkar attended Columbia University, where he studied human dignity and the struggle of blacks against racism. Dr. Ambedkar received his MA and doctorate from Columbia University in 1916, and he was enrolled in the London School of Economics for postdoctoral studies, but he was called back by the Maharaja

and ordered to serve the state for ten years. Ambedkar reached Baroda in September 1917, where he received a warm welcome from the maharaja, but later on he faced the hate of so-called "upper castes" at his workplace. But later on, he became a professor of economics at Sydenham College in November 1918, but the caste of Ambedkar became a problem for him again, and his colleagues never accepted him as a professor before untouchable.

He started a struggle to find the dignity of untouchables; he urged that untouchables are not part of Hinduism because they have not been accepted as human beings rather than slaves; he wanted the abolition of caste; and for this, in 1920, the Maharaja of Kolhapur financed him to start a fortnightly newspaper called "Mooknayak." However, he left Bombay in 1920 to complete his studies at the London School of Economics. In March 1923, he was returned to Bombay, and on March 9, 1924, he became a member of the *Bahishkrit Hitkirini Sabha*, which was established to fight for untouchables' rights; its motto was "Educate, Organize, and Agitate." Dr. Ambedkar became the voice of the untouchables after the three round table conferences, which were held in 1930–1932. He was able to persuade the British government that untouchables were not part of the Hindu religion and that they, like Muslims, required a separate electorate. But Gandhi was against a separate electorate for the untouchables, and as a separate electorate was accepted by the Prime Minister of the United Kingdom, Gandhi went to fast unto death; however, later on, the Poona Pact was made between Gandhi and Ambedkar on the issue of communal award, and some seats were reserved for the untouchables.

He was a feminist, and his relationships with his two wives were friendly. After independence, Nehru invited him to become the Law Minister of the Internal Government, which he accepted. He (Dr. Ambedkar) was the chairman of the Constitution Assembly's drafting committee. He was a great scholar; he knew the principles of democracy and warned that economic and social equality would be the most important components for the success of democracy. Being a law minister, he introduced the Hindu Code Bill in Parliament in 1951. But this bill was not passed by the parliament, and (He) Dr. Ambedkar resigned from the cabinet on September 27, 1951. In 1953, he delivered a divisive speech in the Rajya Sabha, claiming that he was not the maker of the Indian Constitution. I did much against my will. On October 14, 1956, at Nagpur, he was formally initiated into the Buddhist faith with his followers. He founded the Republican Party of India, the same party that

abolished slavery in the United States; his writing work was going on; and on December 6, 1956, three days after completing the manuscript of his monumental work, *Buddha and His Dhamma*, he passed away. Dr. Tharoor wrote this book for those who are new to Dalit Studies as well as those who are interested in learning about the relationships among Dr. Ambedkar, Gandhi, Nehru, and others.

Dr. Tharoor's work is a substantial and valuable addition that should be welcomed for two reasons. First off, it offers a really astute and thorough perspective from someone who has written on sociopolitical issues in Indian society and has worked with the government as a member of parliament. Second, the book displays Dr. Ambedkar's intellectual and understandable explanation as well as the larger outlines of an Indian statesman and is not just a politician's remark on the many subjects in his life. The author of this six-chapter book has divided it into two sections: the first part covers Dr. Ambedkar's life and struggles, and the second section covers Dr. Ambedkar's influence on the coming generations of Dalits. Dalit students have formed a number of associations that have been based on Ambedkar's philosophy, such as the Ambedkarite Students' Association (ASA), the Birsha-Ambedkar-Phule Students' Association (BAPSA), and the Ambedkar-Periyar Study Circle at IIT Madras. These associations have been working for the Dalit assertion. Although the book has not been able to provide all developments in Dalit literature that occurred after Ambedkar, like the concepts of Bahujan and Dalitbahujan, the authors criticise Ambedkar for not working for Adivasis, but they forget that Ambedkar talked about the importance of equality, which shows that Dr. Ambedkar was aware of the conditions of Adivasis, now officially classified as Scheduled Tribes (ST). Therefore, it is required reading for scholars, researchers, and policymakers to understand the problem of dalits and the philosophy of Dr. Ambedkar.